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SOIL FERTILITY STATUS AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN OKEOSE, ILORIN EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, KWARA STATE

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Abstract: *Fertility status of soil samples from OkoOse in Ilorin East LGA of Kwara State were evaluated in this study using twenty soil samples collected at 0 – 20 cm depth and analysed in the laboratory. Mean and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to summarize the data and to compare the means respectively. Findings revealed that the Physico-Chemical properties analysis showed mean values for pH, Potassium, Sodium, Electric Conductivity, Organic matter, and Organic carbon of 6.77, 0.38 (cmol/kg), 0.10 (cmol/kg), 11.90 (dS/cm), 1.00(%), and 0.58 (%) respectively. The mean values of Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Calcium, Magnesium, Exchangeable acidity and Effective Cation Exchange Capacity (ECEC) were 0.12 (%), 72.72 (ppm), 1.15 (cmol/kg), 1.45 (cmol/kg), 0.32 (cmol/kg) and 3.40 (cmol/kg) respectively. The results further reveal that the values of pH, Organic carbon, Nitrogen, Sodium, Calcium, and Magnesium are within the recommended values by the International Agriculture Soil Standard while values of Organic Matter, Available Phosphorus, Potassium, Exchangeable acidity and Effective Cation Exchange Capacity (ECEC) are below the recommended values. However, value of Electrical Conductivity is above the recommended values. In term of textural class, the percentage of sand, silt and clay were 89, 7.00 and 4.00 respectively. This implies that the soil in the area is generally sand soil. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed that there is no significant different in the mean values of the identified parameters. This infers, therefore, that there is no significant difference in the fertility of soil in the area. Generally, the results show that the soil in the area is fertile and good for arable agriculture; especially for planting of cereal crops. The research thus recommends that farmers in the study area should consider planting of crops like maize and guinea-corn. In addition, farmers in the area should consider the use of fertilize to supplement the nutrients that were found to be below the recommended values.*

Keywords: Agriculture, Evaluation, Soil, fertility, Analysis

INTRODUCTION

According to Edwin, and Muthu, (2021) soil fertility is the ability of the soil to provide plant habitat and sustain plant growth. It is the capacity of the soil to provide necessary nutrients to plants in other to promote and sustain plant growth. Soil fertility can also be defined as the ability of the soil to provide available nutrients for crop production (Abbott and Murphy, 2007). Food and Agriculture

Organisation (FAO) of the United Nations (2020) define soil fertility as the ability of the soil to produce and sustain high yields indefinitely. Generally, soil fertility is the ability of the soil to perform agricultural functions.

Soil fertility is fundamental to agricultural sustainability and production. It plays a key role in agricultural productivity. Naumann, et al. (2020) opined that soil fertility is not only

fundamental for sustainable crop production and agricultural development, but it also plays an important role in maintaining ecosystem health. This is because soil fertility is one of the factors that determine the growth and development of crops. The amount of nutrients in the soil has a direct influence on crop output. These soil nutrients can be grouped into macro and micro nutrients. Fertile soil contains the necessary macro and micro nutrients in the appropriate proportion. Soil fertility is critical to crop production because it affects practically all stages of crop growth and development. High crop yield depends on soil fertility. The productivity and health of crops and plants are basically dependent on soil fertility (Nadarajah, 2022). The fertility of soil is essential for securing sustainable food production. Generally, soil is considered fertile when composed of nutrient contents, (like nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K), iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn)), pH level, (the acidity or alkalinity), organic matter, (such as decomposed organic material), microbial activity (breaking down of organic matter by microorganisms like bacteria and fungi) and soil structure (the arrangement of soil particles and pore spaces; and how they are clump together to form aggregates). Therefore, assessing soil fertility is very important for sustainable agricultural production. Spomer, (1982) observed that evaluating soil fertility correctly is fundamental for monitoring soil environment dynamics and improving agricultural productivity. Similarly, Jia, Xiaolin et al, (2023) opined that a precise assessment of soil fertility is essential for monitoring environmental changes, improving agricultural productivity, and achieving sustainable land management and utilization. The soil fertility position is the pillar of the sustainable agricultural production. This is because fertile soil boosts agricultural productivity.

According to Sanchez et al., (1997) cited in Nafiu, et. al. (2012) soil fertility evaluation is the process of estimating the amount of native and residual nutrient elements which could be available for use by growing crops in particular soil and the amount of fertilizer to be supplemented for profitable crop production. Evaluating soil fertility involves analysing soil properties and using the measured values to determine the available nutrients in the soil. Soils vary generally in their fertility because of geologic and climatic variation over space and time. Therefore, for better agricultural productivity, it is essential to evaluate the fertility of the soil. Assessment of the fertility of an agricultural soil speaks greatly about the productive potential of the soil (Nafiu, et al. 2012). The evaluation of soil fertility by selecting the fundamental parameters and their threshold values are necessary to determine the capacity of the soil to perform its agricultural functions.

Low soil fertility has been identified as one of the major constraints in achieving high agricultural productivity. According to Nafiu, et. al. (2012) site-specific evaluation of nutrient fertility status of the soil is very important to rationalise fertilizer use. Accurate site-specific data on soil capability can only be achieved through soil fertility evaluation. Therefore, a better understanding of site-specific evaluation of soil fertility is essential if agricultural production is to be made sustainable in order to meet the needs of the growing population. Thus, it is important to evaluate the ability of soil to provide essential nutrients to plants for healthy growth and optimal yield and to determine its implications on agricultural productivity and sustainability. It is against this background therefore, that this paper is put forward to evaluate soil fertility status and its implications for agricultural productivity in Oke Ose, Ilorin East Local Government Area, Kwara State. The main objectives of the study

are to determine the status of the available main nutrients in the soil and to compare the values with the recommended standard value of soil fertility evaluation index.

The Study Area

Oke Ose is located at the intercept of Latitude $8^{\circ} 55'$ North of the Equator and Longitude $4^{\circ} 65'$ East of the Greenwich Meridian. It is one of the towns in Ilorin East Local Government Area in Kwara State that was created in 1991, has its headquarters in Oke-Oyi and occupies an area of 486 km^2 and with a population of 204,310 at the 2006 census. This population was projected to 311,500 in 2022. The Local Government Area share boundaries with Ilorin South Local Government Area to the south, Ilorin West Local Government Area to the West, Moro Local Government Area to the north and Ifelodun Local Government Area to the east

Figure 1 shows the map of Ilorin East Local Government Area and the study area.

The climate of the area is characterized by wet and dry seasons. The rainy season begins towards the end of April and last till October while the dry season begins in November and ends in March. Temperature in the region range from 33° to 35°C from November to January while from February to April, it ranges from 34° to 37°C Total annual rainfall range from 990.3mm to 1318mm while the relative humidity ranges from 35% to 88%. (Adeniyi and Abubakar, 2020). The geology of the area consists of Precambrian basement complex rocks which are mostly igneous and metamorphic rocks. The soils are mainly loamy with medium fertility. The people of OkeOse are predominantly farmers growing crops such as maize, guinea corn, cassava and yam.

Figure 1: Ilorin East Local Government Area showing the study area

MATERIAL AND METHODS

There are three basic tools for evaluating soil fertility. These are visual symptoms of nutrient deficiency, plant tissue analysis and soil analysis or soil testing. According to Wade, (2010) visual symptoms of nutrient deficiency provides an immediate indication of nutrient status while plant tissue analysis is a laboratory determination of the total elemental content of plants or certain parts of the plant (Steinhilber and Salak, 2010). However, in this study soil analysis was used in evaluation of the soil fertility because it can be used to determine mutually the amount of each nutrient that is immediately available in the soil and the amount that is available from the beginning of development to the death of a crop (Adewale, et al, 2012). Similarly, Nafiu, (2012) reported that soil analysis can also be used to determine both the amount of each nutrient that is immediately available and the amount that can become available during the life of a crop. The objective of soil analysis is to inform farmers of what nutrients are accessible at the start of the planting season; middle of the season, and what nutrient is left at the end of the season. Soil analysis also helps to identify nutritional deficiencies and to determine what needs to be done.

Twenty soil samples were randomly collected with an auger at the depth of 0 – 20 cm. The depth of 0 – 20 cm was adopted because it is the average root depth of cereals crops which are the common crops planted in the area. The soil samples were taken to Lower Niger River Basin Development Authority, Ilorin for laboratory analysis. The samples were air-dried and analysed in the Laboratory using Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC) methods. The physico-chemical properties of the soil were analysed. The following parameters were identified: pH, Potassium, Sodium, Electric Conductivity,

Organic matter, Organic carbon, Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Calcium, Magnesium, Exchangeable acidity, and Effective Cation Exchange Capacity (ECEC). These parameters were selected because they are the common and major soil parameters that determine soil fertility. Both the descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data. Means was used to summarize the data. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare the means in other to determine if they are significantly different from each other.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF SOIL IN OKEOSE

The descriptive analysis of data on soil parameters is presented in table 1. The analysis helps in describing, demonstrating and summarizing the data so as to identify the patterns of the data and relationships between and among the data. Out of the identified soil parameters available phosphorous has the highest mean value (72.72 ppm). This was followed by electrical conductivity (11.90 ds/cm) while sodium has the lowest mean value. The highest standard deviation was obtained in Electrical conductivity. However, coefficient of variation indicates low disparity in the characteristics of parameters examined. The coefficient of variation indicates that electrical conductivity is heterogeneous with values greater than 33% while other parameters are homogeneous with values less than 33%. This implies that the values of electrical conductivity differ significantly. Since the results of the analysis suggest no significant difference in the values of the identified parameters, it can therefore be concluded that there is no significant difference in soil fertility in the study area.

Table 1: Results of the Characteristics of Soil Parameters in the area

Soil Parameters	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
pH (H ₂ O)	6.77	0.12	1.78
Electrical Conductivity (dS/cm)	11.90	4.89	41.12
Organic carbon (%)	0.58	0.04	6.10
Organic matter (%)	1.00	0.06	6.36
Nitrogen (%)	0.12	0.01	11.79
Available Phosphorous (ppm)	72.72	1.65	2.28
Potassium (cmol/kg)	0.38	0.04	9.30
Sodium (cmol/kg)	0.10	0.00	0.00
Calcium (cmol/kg)	1.15	0.07	6.15
Magnesium (cmol/kg)	1.45	0.07	4.88
Exchangeable acidity (cmol/kg)	0.32	0.06	17.68
ECEC (cmol/kg)	3.40	0.02	0.62

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024

The laboratory results obtained were subsequently compared with the values recommended by International Agricultural Soil Standard (Table 2). Result obtained reveals that the values of pH, Organic carbon, Nitrogen, Sodium, Calcium, and Magnesium are within the recommended values by the International Agriculture Soil Standard while values of Organic Matter, Available Phosphorus, Potassium, Exchangeable acidity

and Effective Cation Exchange Capacity (ECEC) are below the recommended values. However, the value of Electrical Conductivity is above the recommended values. This could be as a result of the anthropogenic activities in the area, geological composition and climatic factors. In general, the result of the soil analysis reveals that the soil in the study area is good for agriculture especially in the production of crops like maize, guinea corn, yam and cassava.

Table 2: Results of the Pysico-chemical Analysis of Soil Parameters in the area

Soil Parameters	Depth	Mean	Recommended Values According to International Agriculture Soil Standard
pH (H ₂ O)	0- 20 cm	6.77	6.0 – 7.5
Electrical Conductivity (dS/cm)	0- 20 cm	11.90	0.8 – 1.8, < 4
Organic carbon (%)	0- 20 cm	0.58	0.5 – 3.0,
Organic matter (%)	0- 20 cm	1.00	2 - 4
Nitrogen (%)	0- 20 cm	0.12	0.1 – 2.0
Available Phosphorous (ppm)	0- 20 cm	72.72	20 – 40
Potassium (cmol/kg)	0- 20 cm	0.38	0.75 – 4.75
Sodium (cmol/kg)	0- 20 cm	0.10	0 – 1
Calcium (cmol/kg)	0- 20 cm	1.15	0.5 – 1.5
Magnesium (cmol/kg)	0- 20 cm	1.45	1- 3
Exchangeable acidity (cmol/kg)	0- 20 cm	0.32	10 – 20
ECEC (cmol/kg)	0- 20 cm	3.40	6.63 – 41.65

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024

TEXTURAL CLASSIFICATION OF SOIL IN THE STUDY AREA

The nature of soil texture which is the proportion of sand, silt and clay-sized particles that make up the mineral fraction of soil in the study area is as presented in Table 3. Soil texture is important in soil analysis because it does not only affects soil fertility, but also how

much water soil can hold, how easy and fast water can move through the soil, and how easy to work with the soil. From the table, sand has the highest percentage (89%) followed by silt (7%) and clay (4%). Therefore, in term of soil textural class, the soil in the study area can be classify as sand soil which drain easily and often easy to till and cultivate. However, it required additional fertilization because of low fertility.

Table 3: Soil Textural Classification in the Area

Soil Texture	Depth (cm)	Percentages (%)
Sand (%)	0- 20 cm	89.00
Silt (%)	0- 20 cm	7.00
Clay (%)	0- 20 cm	4.00

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024

VARIABILITY OF SOIL PARAMETERS IN THE STUDY AREA

The result of the Analysis of variance (ANOVA) which shows the differences in the mean values of studied parameters reveals that the p-value of each of the parameters is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). This implies that there is no significant difference in the values of the studied parameters. It can therefore be concluded that the soil in the study area is relatively the same in terms of physico-chemical characteristics.

MANAGEMENT IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESULTS

The findings of this study have several implications for cereal production in the study area:

Firstly, there is a need for soil fertility management practices such as the use of organic and inorganic fertilizers, to improve soil fertility. Secondly, farmers may need to select crop varieties that are tolerant to low soil fertility conditions. Thirdly, an integrated approach can be adopted in managing the nutrient deficiency of soil in the study area; this can be carried out through the use of organic and inorganic fertilizers, crop rotation, and conservation tillage. Finally, there is need for extension services to educate farmers on best management practices for improving soil fertility. Overwhelmingly, the findings of this

study have implications for maize and guinea corn production in OkeOse in Ilorin East LGA of Kwara State, and suggest the need for

integrated soil fertility management practices to improve crop yields.

CONCLUSION

Soil fertility is fundamental to agricultural sustainability and productivity. This study evaluates soil fertility status and its implications on agricultural productivity in Oke Ose, Ilorin East Local Government Area, Kwara State. The result of the study reveals that there is no significant difference in the values of the identified parameters. The mean values of pH, Organic carbon, Nitrogen, Sodium, Calcium, and Magnesium are within the recommended values by the International Agriculture Soil Standard while the mean values of Organic Matter, Available Phosphorus, Potassium, Exchangeable acidity and Effective Cation Exchange Capacity (ECEC) are below the recommended values. Only Electrical Conductivity has mean value above the recommended value which could be as a result of the anthropogenic activities in the area, geological composition and climatic factors. Generally, the results of the analysis reveals that the soil in the area is fertile and good for arable agriculture; especially for planting of cereal crops like maize and guinea corn. Therefore, the paper recommends that

farmers in the study area should consider planting of crops like maize and guinea-corn. In addition, farmers in the area should consider

the use of fertilizer to supplement the nutrients that were found to be below the recommended values.

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